

On the Meshchersky Equation

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ABSTRACT. In this short note we formulate a version of the momentum theorem for the variable mass systems. We deduce the momentum theorem from the fundamental laws of continuum mechanics.

The Main Theorem

Let $D \subset \mathbb{R}^q$ be an open and bounded domain with C^1 -smooth boundary ∂D . The cases $q = 1, 2, 3$ are physically reasonable.

The space \mathbb{R}^q is endowed with an inertial frame of reference Ox^1, \dots, x^q , where $x = (x^1, \dots, x^q)$ are the standard Cartesian coordinates:

$$\mathbf{x} = x^i \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^q.$$

A theorem we formulate below has an invariant form but we use the Cartesian coordinates just for convenience.

Let (\cdot, \cdot) denote the standard inner product in \mathbb{R}^q .

Note also that in the Cartesian frame there is no need to distinguish co- and contravariant components of tensors.

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Let

$$\mathbf{w}(t, x) = w^i(t, x)\mathbf{e}_i, \quad w^i \in C^1(\mathbb{R}^{q+1})$$

stand for a vector field in \mathbb{R}^q and $g_{t_0}^t(x)$ be its flow:

$$\frac{d}{dt}g_{t_0}^t(x) = \mathbf{w}(t, g_{t_0}^t(x)), \quad g_{t_0}^{t_0}(x) = x.$$

We assume that $g_{t_0}^t(x)$ is defined for all real t, t_0 and for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^q$. Introduce a notation

$$D(t) = g_{t_0}^t(D).$$

Loosely speaking \mathbf{w} is a velocity of the volume $D(t)$.

Assume that the domain $D(t)$ is filled with a continuous media with a mass density $\rho(t, x)$ and a flow velocity field $\mathbf{v}(t, x) = v^i(t, x)\mathbf{e}_i$;

$$v^i, \rho \in C^1(\bar{\Omega}), \quad \Omega = \{(t, x) \mid x \in D(t), \quad t \in \mathbb{R}\} \subset \mathbb{R}^{q+1}.$$

The local conservation of mass equation [1] is

$$\rho_t + \operatorname{div}(\rho\mathbf{v}) = 0$$

or

$$\rho_t + \frac{\partial(\rho v^i)}{\partial x^i} = 0. \quad (1.1)$$

Let

$$\mathbf{F}(t, x) = F^i(t, x)\mathbf{e}_i, \quad F^i \in C(\bar{\Omega})$$

stand for a force per unit mass. So that the whole matter in $D(t)$ experiences a net force

$$\mathbf{G}(t) = \int_{D(t)} \rho(t, x)\mathbf{F}(t, x)dV,$$

where dV is the volume element. We denote the stress tensor by $p^{ij}(t, x)$. The boundary $\partial D(t)$ experiences the following external contact net force

$$\mathbf{P}(t) = \int_{\partial D(t)} \mathbf{p}_n dS, \quad \mathbf{p}_n = p^{ij}n_j\mathbf{e}_i,$$

where $\mathbf{n} = n^i\mathbf{e}_i$ is the outer unit normal to $\partial D(t)$; dS is the area element of the surface;

$$p^{ij} \in C^1(\bar{\Omega}).$$

The local equation of linear momentum balance is

$$\rho\left(v_t^k + \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial x^i}v^i\right) = \rho F^k + \frac{\partial p^{kj}}{\partial x^j}. \quad (1.2)$$

Let

$$\mathbf{Q}(t) = \int_{D(t)} \mathbf{v}(t, x)\rho(t, x)dV$$

stand for the linear momentum of $D(t)$.

THEOREM 1. *The equation of linear momentum balance for the volume $D(t)$ is as follows*

$$\dot{\mathbf{Q}} = \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{R},$$

where

$$\mathbf{R} = - \int_{\partial D(t)} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{n}) \rho dS.$$

Proof of the Theorem. By the well-known theorem from the integral calculus and due to (1.2) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} Q^k &= \int_{D(t)} (v_t^k \rho + v^k \rho_t + \operatorname{div}(\rho v^k \mathbf{w})) dV \\ &= \int_{D(t)} \left[\left(F^k - \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial x^j} v^j \right) \rho + \frac{\partial p^{kl}}{\partial x^l} + v^k \rho_t \right] dV \\ &\quad + \int_{D(t)} \operatorname{div}(\rho v^k \mathbf{w}) dV. \end{aligned}$$

Integration by parts gives

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{D(t)} \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial x^j} v^j \rho dV &= \int_{\partial D(t)} v^k v^j n_j \rho dS - \int_{D(t)} v^k \operatorname{div}(\rho \mathbf{v}) dV, \\ \int_{D(t)} \frac{\partial p^{kl}}{\partial x^l} dV &= \int_{\partial D(t)} p^{kl} n_l dS, \\ \int_{D(t)} \operatorname{div}(\rho v^k \mathbf{w}) dV &= \int_{\partial D(t)} \rho v^k w^j n_j dS. \end{aligned}$$

To finish the proof it remains to employ (1.1).

The Theorem is proved.

The angular momentum theorem is derived by the same way:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \int_{D(t)} \mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{v} \rho dV &= \int_{D(t)} \mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{F} \rho dV \\ &\quad + \int_{\partial D(t)} \mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{p}_n dS + \int_{\partial D(t)} \mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{n}) \rho dS. \end{aligned}$$

Here we use $p^{ij} = p^{ji}$.

References

- [1] L. I Sedov: Mechanics of Continuous Media. World Scientific, 1997. Vol. 1.